

Quantum operators of two tetrahedra with a face in common

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Abstract

Following a series of lectures about LQG (loop quantum gravity) held by L. Fatibene (Department of Mathematics, University of Torino (Italy)) in Q1 2024, in this laboratory we will describe the quantum operators of two tetrahedra with a face in common.

We will define the maximal commuting subalgebra of the quantum operators representing the geometric properties of the relevant invariant isotropic subspace. The quantum picture will show a maximal commuting subalgebra of 8 operators against a classical geometric image of 9 degrees of freedom, thus leaving the residual degree of freedom fuzzy.

1 Introduction

In Q1 2024 L. Fatibene (Department of Mathematics, University of Torino (Italy)) held an extensive series of lectures about LQG (loop quantum gravity), refer to [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9]. The series culminated in the representation of the quantum properties of geometry in space.

As an application, in this laboratory we will focus on a composite made of two tetrahedra with a face in common. The pertinent invariant isotropic subspace will be elaborated, a maximal commuting subalgebra capturing the quantum properties of the construction will be worked out and compared to the classical description of the geometry.

2 Representation of the composite

2.1 Isotropic subspace

Let's consider the geometric picture of two tetrahedra, ν_1 and ν_2 , with a face in common. In figure 1 the composite is outlined and the faces labeled. A face is

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labeled against the opposite vertex in each tetrahedron. Faces f_0 and f_7 are in common. Note the identification of the vertices of the face in common.

Figure 1: Outline of two tetrahedra with a face in common

Let's now move to the dual representation, refer to [6]. Each tetrahedron is represented as a node and each face as a link between adjacent tetrahedra, having in common that face, or as a link delimited by a node at one end. Description is in figure 2, γ_0 being the link common to the two tetrahedra, where, as an example, we assume that each link is in the fundamental representation, i.e. $j_0 = j_1 = j_2 = j_3 = j_4 = j_5 = j_6 = \frac{1}{2}$. The links are depicted as incoming to the nodes. Of course, if the common link is incoming to node ν_1 , it will be outgoing from node ν_2 .

Figure 2: Dual representation of the composite

The invariant isotropic subspace, on which the product representation is defined, and whose elements are the intertwiners of the composite, is the tensor product of the invariant isotropic subspaces of each tetrahedron.

Let's consider the tetrahedron ν_1 . As per [6], the isotropic subspace is 2-dimensional and is given by

$$\begin{aligned} w_{\nu_1,1} &= \epsilon^{AB} \epsilon^{CD} e_A \otimes e_B \otimes e_C \otimes e_D \\ w_{\nu_1,2} &= \epsilon^{(AC} \epsilon^{BD)} e_A \otimes e_B \otimes e_C \otimes e_D \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Noting that $\epsilon^{AB} \epsilon^{CD} = (\delta^{AC} \delta^{BD} - \delta^{AD} \delta^{BC})$, we may simplify

$$\begin{aligned} v_1 &= w_{\nu_1,1} = |+-+-\rangle - |+--+\rangle - |-++-\rangle + |-+-+\rangle \\ v_2 &= w_{\nu_1,2} - \frac{1}{2} w_{\nu_1,1} = \epsilon^{AD} \epsilon^{BC} e_A \otimes e_B \otimes e_C \otimes e_D = \\ &= |++--\rangle - |+-+-\rangle - |-+-+\rangle + |--++\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Let's consider the tetrahedron ν_2 . The isotropic subspace is 2-dimensional as well and is given by

$$\begin{aligned} w_{\nu_2,1} &= \delta_E^F \epsilon^{GH} e^E \otimes e_F \otimes e_G \otimes e_H \\ w_{\nu_2,2} &= \delta_E^{(H} \epsilon^{FG)} e^E \otimes e_F \otimes e_G \otimes e_H \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Noting that $\epsilon_{AC} \epsilon^{BC} = \delta_A^B$, we may simplify

$$\begin{aligned} u_1 &= w_{\nu_2,1} = \langle +|+ + - \rangle - \langle +|+ - + \rangle + \langle -|- + - \rangle - \langle -|- - + \rangle \\ u_2 &= w_{\nu_2,2} + \frac{1}{2} w_{\nu_2,1} = \delta_E^G \epsilon^{FH} e^E \otimes e_F \otimes e_G \otimes e_H = \\ &= \langle +|+ + - \rangle - \langle +|+ - + \rangle + \langle -|- + - \rangle - \langle -|- - + \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Hence the invariant isotropic subspace of the composite is 4-dimensional and is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
w_1 &= v_1 \otimes u_1 \\
w_2 &= v_1 \otimes u_2 \\
w_3 &= v_2 \otimes u_1 \\
w_4 &= v_2 \otimes u_2
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

2.2 Operators

As per [7], a brief recall of the Hilbert spaces in LQG.

Let's have an irreducible representation $\rho^{(j)} : SU(2) \rightarrow GL(V_{(j)})$, where the semi-integer j is the spin of the representation, $V_{(j)}$ is the support vector space of dimension $2j + 1$, $V_{(j)}^*$ its dual, $e_\alpha \in V_{(j)}$ a basis, $e^\beta \in V_{(j)}^*$ its dual basis. So, a group element $U \in SU(2)$ can be represented as a tensor $\rho^{(j)}(U)^\alpha_\beta e_\alpha \otimes e^\beta \in V_{(j)} \otimes V_{(j)}^*$.

Let's define a group representation $Sym^n : SU(2) \rightarrow GL(\mathbb{C}^{n+1})$ as the symmetrized tensor product of n copies of the fundamental representation $\rho^{(1/2)} : SU(2) \rightarrow GL(2, \mathbb{C}) : U \rightarrow U_B^A$, let's choose a symmetrized tensor product $e_{A_1} \odot \dots \odot e_{A_n} \in \mathbb{C}^{n+1}$ as a basis; so we have $Sym^n(U) : \mathbb{C}^{n+1} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^{n+1}$ as $Sym^n(U) = U_{(B_1)}^{(A_1)} \dots U_{(B_n)}^{(A_n)} e_{A_1} \odot \dots \odot e_{A_n} \odot e^{B_1} \odot \dots \odot e^{B_n}$. Hence we have $\rho^{(j)} = Sym^{2j}$, i.e. $j = n/2$.

Let's have an abstract lattice $\Gamma = (N, L)$, with N nodes and L links, each link being a pair of nodes, $l = (s_l, t_l)$, called the source node and the target node of the link, respectively. To any link $l \in L$, with a spin j , we associate the vector space $V_l = V_{(j)} \otimes V_{(j)}^*$. A node $\nu \in N$ acts as a source node for outgoing links and as a target node for incoming links. To any node ν , we associate a vector space $V_\nu = V_{(j_1)} \otimes \dots \otimes V_{(j_h)} \otimes V_{(j_1)}^* \otimes \dots \otimes V_{(j_k)}^*$, where j_1, \dots, j_h are the spins of the incoming links, and j_1, \dots, j_k are the spins of the outgoing links.

Let's associate to the lattice the space of functionals $\psi : SU(2)^L \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ as $\psi = i(c)$, where the cylindric tensor c is defined as $\rho^{(j_1)}(U)^\alpha_1 \dots \rho^{(j_l)}(U)^\alpha_l e_{\alpha_1} \otimes \dots \otimes e_{\alpha_l} \otimes e^{\beta_1} \otimes \dots \otimes e^{\beta_l} \in V_{(\Gamma, j_l)}$, and the intertwiner i is a covector $\in V_{(\Gamma, j_l)}^*$. Spin networks are invariant states, which require $i \in Inv(V_{(\Gamma, j_l)}^*)$, and constitute the Hilbert spaces of LQG.

As for operators, they describe observables and, when applied to quantum states, return a relevant measure of the physical state. As per [7], [8], and indicating again a link with a γ , we have the following basic Lie operators

$$\begin{aligned}
(L_{(\nu, \gamma)})_a &= -T\rho^{(j)}(\tau_a) \quad \text{to the right of the representation if } \gamma \text{ is incoming} \\
&\text{or} \\
&= T\rho^{(j)}(\tau_a) \quad \text{to the left of the representation if } \gamma \text{ is outgoing}
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where $\tau_a = -\frac{i}{2}\sigma_a$ (Pauli matrices), $a = x, y, z$; $j = \text{spin of the representation}$.

Moreover we have

$$C_{(\nu)} = \sum_{\gamma} (L_{(\nu, \gamma)})_a = 0 \quad \text{quantum closure condition} \quad (7)$$

Applied to an intertwiner

$$\begin{aligned} (L_{(\nu, \gamma)})_a e^\alpha &= -T \rho^{(j)} (\tau_a)_\mu^\alpha e^\mu \quad \gamma \text{ outgoing} \\ \text{or} \\ (L_{(\nu, \gamma)})_a e_\beta &= T \rho^{(j)} (\tau_a)_\beta^\mu e_\mu \quad \gamma \text{ incoming} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $\alpha = 1, \dots, 2j + 1$.

Note: the coefficients of the transpose representation are the same as the representation, possibly up to a sign.

Specializing to the fundamental representation, i.e. $j = \frac{1}{2}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (L_{(\nu, \gamma)})_a e^A &= -(\tau_a)_B^A e^B \quad \gamma \text{ outgoing} \\ \text{or} \\ (L_{(\nu, \gamma)})_a e_B &= (\tau_a)_B^A e_A \quad \gamma \text{ incoming} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $A = 1, 2$.

On the fundamental representation, with basis $(|+\rangle, |-\rangle)$, the Lie operator acts as

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_x |+\rangle &= -\frac{i}{2} |-\rangle \quad \tau_y |+\rangle = \frac{1}{2} |-\rangle \quad \tau_z |+\rangle = -\frac{i}{2} |+\rangle \quad \tau^2 |+\rangle = -\frac{3}{4} |+\rangle \\ \tau_x |-\rangle &= \frac{i}{2} |+\rangle \quad \tau_y |-\rangle = -\frac{1}{2} |+\rangle \quad \tau_z |-\rangle = \frac{i}{2} |-\rangle \quad \tau^2 |-\rangle = -\frac{3}{4} |-\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where $\tau^2 = \vec{\tau} \cdot \vec{\tau}$.

On a generic representation of spin j , we have

$$\tau^2 = -j(j+1)\mathbb{I} \quad (11)$$

The commutator of the Lie operators is

$$[(L_{(\nu, \gamma)})_a, (L_{(\nu', \gamma')})_b] = -\delta_{\nu\nu'} \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \epsilon_{ab}{}^c (L_{(\nu, \gamma)})_c \quad (12)$$

We can use the Lie operators to define invariant operators, that is operators which commute with the closure operator $C_{(\nu)}$, refer to equation (7), or with the closure operator of the composite, refer to equation (36), if the Lie operators refer to different nodes, and thus preserve the invariant subspace, i.e. the intertwiners, refer to [9], as

$$D_{(\nu, \gamma; \nu', \gamma')} = \vec{L}_{(\nu, \gamma)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu', \gamma')} \quad (13)$$

That allows us to define the following adimensional observables

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{(\nu,\gamma)} &= \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \quad \text{adimensional squared area} \\
D_{(\nu,\gamma;\nu',\gamma')} &= \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu',\gamma')} \quad \text{dihedral angle} \\
V_{(\nu)}^2 &= \frac{2}{9} [D_{(\nu,\gamma_i\gamma_k)}, D_{(\nu,\gamma_i\gamma_j)}] \quad \text{adimensional squared volume}
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

where $i \neq j \neq k$, independent links in node ν .

Note that

$$V_{(\nu)} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} (D_{(\nu)})^{1/2} \tag{15}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{(\nu)} = D_{(\nu,ijk)} &= \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_i)} \cdot (\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_j)} \times \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_k)}) = \frac{1}{2} [\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_i)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_k)}, (\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_i)} + \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_j)})^2] = \\
&= [\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_i)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_k)}, \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_i)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_j)}] = [D_{(\nu,\gamma_i\gamma_k)}, D_{(\nu,\gamma_i\gamma_j)}] \\
&\text{unchanged, by definition, under a circular shift of } i, j, k
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

so, last line in equation (14) follows.

Moreover, considering $i \neq j \neq k \neq h$, links in node ν , and equation (7), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{(\nu,ijh)} &= \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_i)} \cdot (\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_j)} \times \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_h)}) = \\
&= -\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_i)} \cdot (\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_j)} \times (\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_i)} + \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_j)} + \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_k)})) = \\
&= -\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_i)} \cdot (\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_j)} \times \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_k)}) = -D_{(\nu,ijk)} = -D_{(\nu)}
\end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

Above definitions are justified considering the conjugate momentum p of the Holst Lagrangian L_H , against the connection variable A , which is given up to a constant by the densitized triad E , refer to [3]. The densitized triad is classically a 2-form, of which the flow through a surface measures the surface area, refer to [8]. If we display the momentum in the quantum approach and apply the functional derivative to the link representation, refer to [5], we have

$$\begin{aligned}
p &= \frac{\delta L_H}{\delta A} = \frac{1}{\kappa\gamma_H} E \\
\int_{Surface} E &= \text{Surface area} \\
p &= -i\hbar \frac{\delta}{\delta A} \\
E &= -i\hbar\kappa\gamma_H \frac{\delta}{\delta A} = -i\hbar\kappa\gamma_H \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)}
\end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

where $\kappa = \frac{8\pi G}{c^3}$, γ_H Holst parameter.

Thus we can define the following operator, refer to [8],

$$\begin{aligned}
(E_{(\gamma)})^2 &= \vec{E}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \cdot \vec{E}_{(\nu,\gamma)} = -(\hbar\kappa\gamma_H)^2 \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} = \\
&= -(\hbar\kappa\gamma_H)^2 \tau^2 = (\hbar\kappa\gamma_H)^2 j(j+1)\mathbb{I}
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

Eigenvalues of $(E_{(\gamma)})^2$ are positive, so we can define the area operator

$$A_{(\gamma)} = \sqrt{(E_{(\gamma)})^2} = (\hbar\kappa\gamma_H)\sqrt{j(j+1)}\mathbb{I} = a_0\sqrt{j(j+1)}\mathbb{I} \quad (20)$$

Note that $a_0 = \hbar\kappa\gamma_H$ has the dimensions of an area, in particular $a_0 = 0.6567\gamma_H \times 10^{-68}m^2$.

Therefore, by associating the a_0 parameter to the Lie operator $\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)}$, we can construct the dimensional area and volume operators. That is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{adimensional} &\rightarrow \text{dimensional} \\ \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} &\rightarrow -ia_0\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \\ \text{adimensional squared area} &\rightarrow \text{dimensional squared area} \\ \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} &\rightarrow -a_0^2\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \\ \text{adimensional squared volume} &\rightarrow \text{dimensional squared volume} \\ \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_i)} \cdot (\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_j)} \times \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_k)}) &\rightarrow ia_0^3\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_i)} \cdot (\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_j)} \times \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_k)}) \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

A further comment about the dihedral angle. In order to read the cosine of an angle, we have to normalize it, that is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{dihedral angle} &\rightarrow \text{normalized dihedral angle} \\ D_{(\nu,\gamma;\nu',\gamma')} &\rightarrow \frac{D_{(\nu,\gamma;\nu',\gamma')}}{\sqrt{|\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)}|}\sqrt{|\vec{L}_{(\nu',\gamma')} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu',\gamma')}|}} \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

hence

$$\text{angular measure (radians)} = \arccos\left(\frac{D_{(\nu,\gamma;\nu',\gamma')}}{\sqrt{|\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)}|}\sqrt{|\vec{L}_{(\nu',\gamma')} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu',\gamma')}|}}\right) \quad (23)$$

Note also that the angular measure from a normalized dihedral angle is between the outer normals to the faces of a tetrahedron. The angular measure between the faces is the complement to π radians or to 180° of the former.

2.3 Commutators

In order to set a maximal commuting subalgebra, we have to compute the commutators between the invariant operators. In figure 3 again the dual representation of the composite, however with just the links and labeled by generic indices. Of course, $h \neq i \neq j \neq k \neq l \neq m \neq n$. Let's simplify a little bit the notation indicating each γ in the operators with just the corresponding index.

Figure 3: Dual representation of the composite (links only)

We will first compute the commutation relations between operators of a single tetrahedron, let's say ν_1 , and then involving operators acting on both the tetrahedra, i.e. dihedral angles between a link in tetrahedron ν_1 and another link in tetrahedron ν_2 . Let's call these latter: shared dihedral angles.

Tetrahedron ν_1 , squared area vs. squared area operators:

$$\begin{aligned}
 [D_{\nu_1,ii}, D_{\nu_1,jj}] &= [\vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,i}, \vec{L}_{\nu_1,j} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,j}] = 0 \quad \text{no link match} \\
 [D_{\nu_1,ii}, D_{\nu_1,hh}] &= [D_{\nu_1,ii}, D_{\nu_1,ii} + D_{\nu_1,jj} + D_{\nu_1,kk} + 2(D_{\nu_1,ij} + D_{\nu_1,ik} + D_{\nu_1,jk})] = 0 \\
 & \quad h \text{ vs. } i, j, k, \text{ refer to equation (7);} \\
 & \quad \text{squared areas commute with squared areas, refer to first equation;} \\
 & \quad \text{squared areas commute with dihedral angles, refer to equation (25);} \\
 & \quad \text{each operator commutes with itself}
 \end{aligned}$$

(24)

Tetrahedron ν_1 , squared area vs. dihedral angle operators:

$$\begin{aligned}
[D_{\nu_1,ii}, D_{\nu_1,jk}] &= [\vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,i}, \vec{L}_{\nu_1,j} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,k}] = 0 \quad \text{no link match} \\
[D_{\nu_1,ii}, D_{\nu_1,ij}] &= [\vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,i}, \vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,j}] = \\
&= -\epsilon_{ab}{}^c ((L_i)_a (L_j)_b (L_i)_c + (L_i)_c (L_j)_b (L_i)_a) = 0 \\
&\quad \text{1st factor antisymmetric in } a, c, \text{ 2nd symmetric} \\
[D_{\nu_1,hh}, D_{\nu_1,ij}] &= [D_{\nu_1,ii} + D_{\nu_1,jj} + D_{\nu_1,kk} + 2(D_{\nu_1,ij} + D_{\nu_1,ik} + D_{\nu_1,jk}), D_{\nu_1,ij}] = \\
&= 2[D_{\nu_1,ik} + D_{\nu_1,jk}, D_{\nu_1,ij}] = 0 \\
&\quad h \text{ vs. } i, j, k, \text{ refer to equation (7);} \\
&\quad \text{squared areas commute with dihedral angles, refer to first two equations;} \\
&\quad \text{each operator commutes with itself;} \\
&\quad \text{dihedral angles do not commute with dihedral angles, refer equation (27),} \\
&\quad \text{but the two terms offset each other} \\
[D_{\nu_1,ii}, D_{\nu_1,jh}] &= -[D_{\nu_1,ii}, D_{\nu_1,ji} + D_{\nu_1,jj} + D_{\nu_1,jk}] = 0 \\
&\quad h \text{ vs. } i, j, k, \text{ refer to equation (7);} \\
&\quad \text{squared areas commute with squared areas, refer to equation (24);} \\
&\quad \text{squared areas commute with dihedral angles, refer to first two equations} \\
[D_{\nu_1,ii}, D_{\nu_1,ih}] &= -[D_{\nu_1,ii}, D_{\nu_1,ii} + D_{\nu_1,ij} + D_{\nu_1,ik}] = 0 \\
&\quad h \text{ vs. } i, j, k, \text{ refer to equation (7);} \\
&\quad \text{squared areas commute with squared areas, refer to equation (24);} \\
&\quad \text{squared areas commute with dihedral angles, refer to first two equations} \\
[D_{\nu_1,hh}, D_{\nu_1,ih}] &= -[D_{\nu_1,hh}, D_{\nu_1,ii} + D_{\nu_1,ij} + D_{\nu_1,ik}] = 0 \\
&\quad h \text{ vs. } i, j, k, \text{ refer to equation (7);} \\
&\quad \text{squared area } hh \text{ commutes with squared areas, refer to equation (24);} \\
&\quad \text{squared area } hh \text{ commutes with dihedral angles, refer to third equation} \\
\end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

Tetrahedron ν_1 , squared area vs. squared volume operators:

$$\begin{aligned}
[D_{\nu_1,ii}, D_{\nu_1}] &= [\vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,i}, [D_{\nu_1,ik}, D_{\nu_1,ij}]] = \\
&= [\vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,i}, [\vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,k}, \vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,j}]] = \\
&= \epsilon_{ad}{}^e \epsilon_{bc}{}^d ((L_i)_a (L_i)_e (L_j)_c (L_k)_b + (L_i)_e (L_i)_a (L_j)_c (L_k)_b) = 0 \\
&\quad \text{1st factor antisymmetric in } a, e, \text{ 2nd symmetric} \\
[D_{\nu_1,hh}, D_{\nu_1}] &= [D_{\nu_1,ii} + D_{\nu_1,jj} + D_{\nu_1,kk} + 2(D_{\nu_1,ij} + D_{\nu_1,ik} + D_{\nu_1,jk}), D_{\nu_1}] = \\
&= 2[D_{\nu_1,ij} + D_{\nu_1,ik} + D_{\nu_1,jk}, D_{\nu_1}] = 0 \\
&\quad h \text{ vs. } i, j, k, \text{ refer to equation (7);} \\
&\quad \text{squared areas commute with squared volume, refer to first equation;} \\
&\quad \text{dihedral angles vs. squared volume show Jacobi identity (refer} \\
&\quad \text{to equation (28), apply a circular shift to } i, j, k, \text{ and then add up)} \\
\end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

Tetrahedron ν_1 , dihedral angle vs. dihedral angle operators:

$$\begin{aligned}
[D_{\nu_1,ij}, D_{\nu_1,ik}] &= [\vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,j}, \vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,k}] = \\
&= -\epsilon_{ab}{}^c (L_i)_c (L_j)_a (L_k)_b = \\
&= -\vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot (\vec{L}_{\nu_1,j} \times \vec{L}_{\nu_1,k}) = -D_{\nu_1} \quad \text{does not commute} \\
[D_{\nu_1,ij}, D_{\nu_1,ih}] &= -[D_{\nu_1,ij}, D_{\nu_1,ii} + D_{\nu_1,ij} + D_{\nu_1,ik}] = \\
&= -[D_{\nu_1,ij}, D_{\nu_1,ik}] = D_{\nu_1} \quad \text{does not commute} \\
&h \text{ vs. } i, j, k, \text{ refer to equation (7);} \\
&\text{squared areas commute with dihedral angles, refer to equation (25);} \\
&\text{each operator commutes with itself} \\
[D_{\nu_1,ij}, D_{\nu_1,kh}] &= -[D_{\nu_1,ij}, D_{\nu_1,ki} + D_{\nu_1,kj} + D_{\nu_1,kl}] = \\
&= -[D_{\nu_1,ij}, D_{\nu_1,ki} + D_{\nu_1,kj}] = 0 \\
&h \text{ vs. } i, j, k, \text{ refer to equation (7);} \\
&\text{squared areas commute with dihedral angles, refer to equation (25);} \\
&\text{dihedral angles do not commute with dihedral angles, refer to first equation,} \\
&\text{but the two terms offset each other}
\end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

Tetrahedron ν_1 , dihedral angle vs. squared volume operators:

$$\begin{aligned}
[D_{\nu_1,ij}, D_{\nu_1}] &= [\vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,j}, [D_{\nu_1,ik}, D_{\nu_1,ij}]] = \\
&= [\vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,j}, [\vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,k}, \vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,j}]] = \\
&= \epsilon_{ac}{}^e \epsilon_{bc}{}^d (L_i)_a (L_i)_d (L_j)_e (L_k)_b + \epsilon_{ad}{}^e \epsilon_{bc}{}^d (L_i)_e (L_j)_c (L_j)_a (L_k)_b = \\
&= D_{\nu_1,ik} (D_{\nu_1,ij} + D_{\nu_1,jj}) - (D_{\nu_1,ii} + D_{\nu_1,ij}) D_{\nu_1,jk} \quad \text{does not commute} \\
[D_{\nu_1,ih}, D_{\nu_1}] &= -[D_{\nu_1,ii} + D_{\nu_1,ij} + D_{\nu_1,ik}, D_{\nu_1}] = \\
&= [D_{\nu_1,jk}, D_{\nu_1}] = \\
&= D_{\nu_1,ji} (D_{\nu_1,jk} + D_{\nu_1,kk}) - (D_{\nu_1,jj} + D_{\nu_1,jk}) D_{\nu_1,ki} \quad \text{does not commute} \\
&h \text{ vs. } i, j, k, \text{ refer to equation (7);} \\
&\text{squared areas commute with squared volume, refer to equation (26);} \\
&\text{dihedral angles vs. squared volume show Jacobi identity (refer} \\
&\text{to first equation, apply a circular shift to } i, j, k, \text{ and then add up)}
\end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

Tetrahedron ν_1 , squared volume vs. squared volume operators:

$$\begin{aligned}
[D_{\nu_1,ijk}, D_{\nu_1,ijh}] &= -[D_{\nu_1,ijk}, D_{\nu_1,iji} + D_{\nu_1,ijj} + D_{\nu_1,ijk}] = 0 \\
&h \text{ vs. } i, j, k, \text{ refer to equation (7);} \\
&\text{If two indices in the squared volume are equal, it vanishes;} \\
&\text{each operator commutes with itself}
\end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

Tetrahedron ν_1 / tetrahedron ν_2 shared dihedral angle vs. tetrahedron ν_1

squared area operators:

$$\begin{aligned}
[D_{\nu_1,j;\nu_2,l}, D_{\nu_1,ii}] &= [\vec{L}_{\nu_1,j} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_2,l}, \vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,i}] = 0 \quad \text{no match, either link or node} \\
[D_{\nu_1,i;\nu_2,l}, D_{\nu_1,ii}] &= [\vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_2,l}, \vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,i}] = \\
&= -\epsilon_{ab}^c ((L_{\nu_1,i})_b (L_{\nu_1,i})_c (L_{\nu_2,l})_a + (L_{\nu_1,i})_c (L_{\nu_1,i})_b (L_{\nu_2,l})_a) = 0 \\
&\quad \text{1st factor antisymmetric in } b, c, \text{ 2nd symmetric} \\
[D_{\nu_1,h;\nu_2,l}, D_{\nu_1,ii}] &= -[D_{\nu_1,i;\nu_2,l} + D_{\nu_1,j;\nu_2,l} + D_{\nu_1,k;\nu_2,l}, D_{\nu_1,ii}] = 0 \\
&\quad h \text{ vs. } i, j, k, \text{ refer to equation (7);} \\
&\quad \text{shared dihedral angles commute with squared areas,} \\
&\quad \text{refer to second equation;} \\
&\quad \text{no match, either link or node} \\
[D_{\nu_1,i;\nu_2,l}, D_{\nu_1,hh}] &= [D_{\nu_1,i;\nu_2,l}, D_{\nu_1,ii} + D_{\nu_1,jj} + D_{\nu_1,kk} + 2(D_{\nu_1,ij} + D_{\nu_1,ik} + D_{\nu_1,jk})] = \\
&= 2[D_{\nu_1,i;\nu_2,l}, D_{\nu_1,ij} + D_{\nu_1,ik}] = \\
&= 2\vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot ((\vec{L}_{\nu_1,j} + \vec{L}_{\nu_1,k}) \times \vec{L}_{\nu_2,l}) \quad \text{does not commute} \\
&\quad h \text{ vs. } i, j, k, \text{ refer to equation (7);} \\
&\quad \text{shared dihedral angles commute with squared areas,} \\
&\quad \text{refer to second equation;} \\
&\quad \text{no match, either link or node;} \\
&\quad \text{shared dihedral angles do not commute with dihedral angles,} \\
&\quad \text{if one link in common, refer to equation (31)}
\end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

Tetrahedron ν_1 / tetrahedron ν_2 shared dihedral angle vs. tetrahedron ν_1 dihedral angle operators:

$$\begin{aligned}
[D_{\nu_1,i;\nu_2,l}, D_{\nu_1,jk}] &= [\vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_2,l}, \vec{L}_{\nu_1,j} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,k}] = 0 \quad \text{no match, either link or node} \\
[D_{\nu_1,i;\nu_2,l}, D_{\nu_1,ij}] &= [\vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_2,l}, \vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1,j}] = \\
&= -\epsilon_{ab}^c (L_{\nu_1,i})_c (L_{\nu_1,j})_b (L_{\nu_2,l})_a = \\
&= \vec{L}_{\nu_1,i} \cdot (\vec{L}_{\nu_1,j} \times \vec{L}_{\nu_2,l}) \quad \text{does not commute} \\
[D_{\nu_1,h;\nu_2,l}, D_{\nu_1,ij}] &= -[D_{\nu_1,i;\nu_2,l} + D_{\nu_1,j;\nu_2,l} + D_{\nu_1,k;\nu_2,l}, D_{\nu_1,ij}] = \\
&= -[D_{\nu_1,i;\nu_2,l} + D_{\nu_1,j;\nu_2,l}, D_{\nu_1,ij}] = 0 \\
&\quad h \text{ vs. } i, j, k, \text{ refer to equation (7);} \\
&\quad \text{no match, either link or node;} \\
&\quad \text{shared dihedral angles do not commute with dihedral angles,} \\
&\quad \text{if one link in common, refer to second equation,} \\
&\quad \text{but the two terms offset each other}
\end{aligned} \tag{31}$$

Tetrahedron ν_1 / tetrahedron ν_2 shared dihedral angle vs. tetrahedron ν_1

squared volume operators:

$$\begin{aligned}
[D_{\nu_1, i; \nu_2, l}, D_{\nu_1}] &= [\vec{L}_{\nu_1, i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_2, l}, [D_{\nu_1, ik}, D_{\nu_1, ij}]] = \\
&= [\vec{L}_{\nu_1, i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_2, l}, [\vec{L}_{\nu_1, i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1, k}, \vec{L}_{\nu_1, i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1, j}]] = \\
&= \epsilon_{ad}^e \epsilon_{bc}^d (L_{\nu_1, i})_e (L_{\nu_1, j})_c (L_{\nu_1, k})_b (L_{\nu_2, l})_a = \\
&= -D_{\nu_1, ij} D_{\nu_1, k; \nu_2, l} + D_{\nu_1, ik} D_{\nu_1, j; \nu_2, l} \quad \text{does not commute} \\
[D_{\nu_1, h; \nu_2, l}, D_{\nu_1}] &= -[D_{\nu_1, i; \nu_2, l} + D_{\nu_1, j; \nu_2, l} + D_{\nu_1, k; \nu_2, l}, D_{\nu_1}] = 0 \\
&h \text{ vs. } i, j, k, \text{ refer to equation (7);} \\
&\text{shared dihedral angles vs. squared volume show Jacobi identity (refer} \\
&\text{to first equation, apply a circular shift to } i, j, k, \text{ and then add up)}
\end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

Tetrahedron ν_1 / tetrahedron ν_2 shared dihedral angle vs. shared dihedral angle operators:

$$\begin{aligned}
[D_{\nu_1, i; \nu_2, l}, D_{\nu_1, j; \nu_2, m}] &= [\vec{L}_{\nu_1, i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_2, l}, \vec{L}_{\nu_1, j} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_2, m}] = 0 \quad \text{no match, either link or node} \\
[D_{\nu_1, i; \nu_2, l}, D_{\nu_1, i; \nu_2, m}] &= [\vec{L}_{\nu_1, i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_2, l}, \vec{L}_{\nu_1, i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_2, m}] = \\
&= -\epsilon_{ab}^c (L_{\nu_1, i})_c (L_{\nu_2, l})_a (L_{\nu_2, m})_b = \\
&= -\vec{L}_{\nu_1, i} \cdot (\vec{L}_{\nu_2, l} \times \vec{L}_{\nu_2, m}) \quad \text{does not commute} \\
[D_{\nu_1, h; \nu_2, l}, D_{\nu_1, i; \nu_2, m}] &= -[D_{\nu_1, i; \nu_2, l} + D_{\nu_1, j; \nu_2, l} + D_{\nu_1, k; \nu_2, l}, D_{\nu_1, i; \nu_2, m}] = \\
&= -[D_{\nu_1, i; \nu_2, l}, D_{\nu_1, i; \nu_2, m}] = \\
&= \vec{L}_{\nu_1, i} \cdot (\vec{L}_{\nu_2, l} \times \vec{L}_{\nu_2, m}) \quad \text{does not commute} \\
&h \text{ vs. } i, j, k, \text{ refer to equation (7);} \\
&\text{no match, either link or node;} \\
&\text{shared dihedral angles do not commute with shared dihedral angles,} \\
&\text{if one link in common, refer to second equation}
\end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

A remarkable relation is stated if we consider the geometric meaning of the squared area and dihedral angle operators, refer to equation (14), and focus on the face in common between the two tetrahedra.

In fact

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{\nu_1, hh} &= D_{\nu_2, hh} \quad \text{i.e.} \quad \vec{L}_{\nu_1, h} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1, h} = \vec{L}_{\nu_2, h} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_2, h} \\
D_{\nu_1, ih} &= -D_{\nu_1, i; \nu_2, h} \quad \text{i.e.} \quad \vec{L}_{\nu_1, i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_1, h} = -\vec{L}_{\nu_1, i} \cdot \vec{L}_{\nu_2, h}
\end{aligned} \tag{34}$$

so

$$\vec{L}_{\nu_1, h} = -\vec{L}_{\nu_2, h} \tag{35}$$

Considering the quantum closure condition of each tetrahedron, we have

$$\vec{L}_{\nu_1, h} + \vec{L}_{\nu_2, h} = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \vec{L}_{\nu_1, i} + \vec{L}_{\nu_1, j} + \vec{L}_{\nu_1, k} + \vec{L}_{\nu_2, l} + \vec{L}_{\nu_2, m} + \vec{L}_{\nu_2, n} = 0 \tag{36}$$

This is the quantum closure condition, applied to the composite.

2.4 Maximal commuting subalgebra

In order to set a maximal commuting subalgebra, here the commutation compatibility between the operators, as stated in subsection 2.3.

Squared area operators commute with:

- squared areas (including $D_{\nu_1, hh}$)
- dihedral angles (including $D_{\nu_1, hh}$ and $D_{\nu_1, ih}$)
- squared volume (including $D_{\nu_1, hh}$)
- shared dihedral angles (including $D_{\nu_1, h; \nu_2, l}$, however $[D_{\nu_1, i; \nu_2, l}, D_{\nu_1, hh}]$ does not commute)

Dihedral angle operators do not commute with:

- dihedral angles (however $[D_{\nu_1, ij}, D_{\nu_1, kh}]$ commutes)
- squared volume (including $D_{\nu_1, ih}$)
- shared dihedral angles, if one link in common (however $[D_{\nu_1, h; \nu_2, l}, D_{\nu_1, ij}]$ commutes)

Squared volume operator commutes with:

- squared volume

does not commute with:

- shared dihedral angles (however $[D_{\nu_1, h; \nu_2, l}, D_{\nu_1}]$ commutes)

Shared dihedral angle operators do not commute with:

- shared dihedral angles, if one link in common (including $[D_{\nu_1, h; \nu_2, l}, D_{\nu_1, i; \nu_2, m}]$)

2.4.1 Single tetrahedron

As for a single tetrahedron, possible sets of a maximal commuting subalgebra are:

- $(D_{\nu_1, ii}, D_{\nu_1, jj}, D_{\nu_1, kk}, D_{\nu_1, hh}, D_{\nu_1, ij})$ 4 squared areas + 1 dihedral angle
We could think to add also $D_{\nu_1, kh}$, which is commuting, however it is not linearly independent from the others; in fact $D_{\nu_1, kh} = -(D_{\nu_1, ki} + D_{\nu_1, kj} + D_{\nu_1, kk})$, that is $(D_{\nu_1, ki} + D_{\nu_1, kj}) = -(D_{\nu_1, kh} + D_{\nu_1, kk})$, hence $D_{\nu_1, hh} = D_{\nu_1, ii} + D_{\nu_1, jj} - D_{\nu_1, kk} + 2D_{\nu_1, ij} - 2D_{\nu_1, kh}$.
- $(D_{\nu_1, ii}, D_{\nu_1, jj}, D_{\nu_1, kk}, D_{\nu_1, ij}, D_{\nu_1, kh})$ 3 squared areas + 2 dihedral angles
We could try to add also the D_{ν_1} , that is the squared volume $V_{\nu_1}^2$, which commutes with the squared areas (including $D_{\nu_1, hh}$), but it does not commute with dihedral angles (including $D_{\nu_1, ih}$, where i stands for i , or j , or k).
- $(D_{\nu_1, ii}, D_{\nu_1, jj}, D_{\nu_1, kk}, D_{\nu_1, hh}, V_{\nu_1}^2)$ 4 squared areas + 1 squared volume

Therefore, as for a single tetrahedron, the maximal commuting subalgebra shows 5 quantum operators against 6 classical degrees of freedom, refer to appendix A.1, leaving one geometric property fuzzy.

2.4.2 Composite

As for the composite, the operators involving the common link h refer to a measure internal to each tetrahedron, hence we disregard them. Possible sets of a maximal commuting subalgebra are:

- $(D_{\nu_1,ii}, D_{\nu_1,jj}, D_{\nu_1,kk}, D_{\nu_1,ij}, D_{\nu_2,ll}, D_{\nu_2,mm}, D_{\nu_2,nn}, D_{\nu_2,lm})$ ν_1 : 3 squared areas + 1 dihedral angle + ν_2 : 3 squared areas + 1 dihedral angle
- $(D_{\nu_1,ii}, D_{\nu_1,jj}, D_{\nu_1,kk}, D_{\nu_1,ij}, D_{\nu_2,ll}, D_{\nu_2,mm}, D_{\nu_2,nn}, V_{\nu_2}^2)$ ν_1 : 3 squared areas + 1 dihedral angle + ν_2 : 3 squared areas + 1 volume
- $(D_{\nu_1,ii}, D_{\nu_1,jj}, D_{\nu_1,kk}, V_{\nu_1}^2, D_{\nu_2,ll}, D_{\nu_2,mm}, D_{\nu_2,nn}, D_{\nu_2,lm})$ ν_1 : 3 squared areas + 1 squared volume + ν_2 : 3 squared areas + 1 dihedral angle
- $(D_{\nu_1,ii}, D_{\nu_1,jj}, D_{\nu_1,kk}, V_{\nu_1}^2, D_{\nu_2,ll}, D_{\nu_2,mm}, D_{\nu_2,nn}, V_{\nu_2}^2)$ ν_1 : 3 squared areas + 1 squared volume + ν_2 : 3 squared areas + 1 squared volume
- $(D_{\nu_1,ii}, D_{\nu_1,jj}, D_{\nu_1,kk}, D_{\nu_1,ij}, D_{\nu_2,ll}, D_{\nu_2,mm}, D_{\nu_2,nn}, D_{\nu_1,k;\nu_2,l})$ ν_1 : 3 squared areas + 1 dihedral angle + ν_2 : 3 squared areas + ν_1/ν_2 : 1 shared dihedral angle
Instead of $D_{\nu_1,k;\nu_2,l}$, we could have used $D_{\nu_1,k;\nu_2,m}$, or $D_{\nu_1,k;\nu_2,n}$ as well.
- $(D_{\nu_1,ii}, D_{\nu_1,jj}, D_{\nu_1,kk}, D_{\nu_2,ll}, D_{\nu_2,mm}, D_{\nu_2,nn}, D_{\nu_2,lm}, D_{\nu_1,i;\nu_2,n})$ ν_1 : 3 squared areas + ν_2 : 3 squared areas + 1 dihedral angle + ν_1/ν_2 : 1 shared dihedral angle
Instead of $D_{\nu_1,i;\nu_2,n}$, we could have used $D_{\nu_1,j;\nu_2,n}$, or $D_{\nu_1,k;\nu_2,n}$ as well.
- $(D_{\nu_1,ii}, D_{\nu_1,jj}, D_{\nu_1,kk}, D_{\nu_2,ll}, D_{\nu_2,mm}, D_{\nu_2,nn}, D_{\nu_1,i;\nu_2,l}, D_{\nu_1,j;\nu_2,m})$ ν_1 : 3 squared areas + ν_2 : 3 squared areas + ν_1/ν_2 : 2 shared dihedral angle
We could have used $D_{\nu_1,k;\nu_2,n}$, replacing one of the two shared dihedral angles, but not all of the three together. Reason is that they are not linearly independent, refer to equation (36).

Therefore, as for the composite, the maximal commuting subalgebra shows 8 quantum operators against 9 classical degrees of freedom, refer to appendix A.2, leaving one geometric property fuzzy.

Appendix

A.1 Classical geometry of a single tetrahedron

Figure 4: Single tetrahedron (outer normals shown)

A single tetrahedron is classically sketched in figure 4. It is a 3-simplex described by 4 vertices:

$$\nu_1 = [x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3] \quad (37)$$

it shows 4 oriented faces (oriented triangles), which are 2-simplices, and that we label against the opposite vertex

$$f_0 = [x_1, x_2, x_3] \quad f_1 = -[x_0, x_2, x_3] \quad f_2 = [x_0, x_1, x_3] \quad f_3 = -[x_0, x_1, x_2] \quad (38)$$

each face has a boundary of 3 (oriented) sides, which are 1-simplices

$$\begin{aligned} \partial f_0 &= [x_2, x_3] - [x_1, x_3] + [x_1, x_2] & \partial f_1 &= -[x_2, x_3] + [x_0, x_3] - [x_0, x_2] \\ \partial f_2 &= [x_1, x_3] - [x_0, x_3] + [x_0, x_1] & \partial f_3 &= -[x_1, x_2] + [x_0, x_2] - [x_0, x_1] \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

As for the sides

$$\begin{aligned} s_{01} &= [x_0, x_1] & s_{02} &= [x_0, x_2] & s_{03} &= [x_0, x_3] \\ s_{12} &= [x_1, x_2] & s_{13} &= [x_1, x_3] & s_{23} &= [x_2, x_3] \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

however

$$s_{ij} = [x_i, x_j] = [x_i, x_0] + [x_0, x_j] = s_{0j} - s_{0i} \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3 \quad (41)$$

hence only 3 sides are independent.

A tetrahedron is determined by an origin, one of the vertices, and the other 3 vertices, i.e. $4 \times 3 = 12$ numbers up to translations and rotations, that is $3 + 3 = 6$ numbers, hence giving $12 - 6 = 6$ degrees of freedom.

Sides representation

Alternatively, we can choose an origin and 3 independent sides s_{0i} , i.e. $3 + 3 \times 3 = 3 + 9 = 12$ numbers up to translations and rotations, that is 6 numbers, hence giving again 6 degrees of freedom.

Faces representation

There is another representation of the geometry in terms of the 4 normals \vec{l}_α to the faces f_α , where $\alpha = 0, 1, 2, 3$. Let's consider the outer normals

$$\vec{l}_0 = \frac{1}{2}s_{12} \times s_{13} \quad \vec{l}_1 = -\frac{1}{2}s_{02} \times s_{03} \quad \vec{l}_2 = \frac{1}{2}s_{01} \times s_{03} \quad \vec{l}_3 = -\frac{1}{2}s_{01} \times s_{02} \quad (42)$$

Note: choice of sign and order is combinatorial. Take the boundary of the face, discard the first side keeping the sign on one side, take the vector product of the second with the third side, and finally rearrange factors.

$$\sum_{\alpha} \vec{l}_\alpha = 0 \quad \text{classical closure condition} \quad (43)$$

Only 3 normals are independent.

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{l}_1 &= -\frac{1}{2}s_{02} \times s_{03} & s_{01} &= \sqrt{2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{d}} \vec{l}_2 \times \vec{l}_3 \\ \vec{l}_2 &= -\frac{1}{2}s_{03} \times s_{01} & s_{02} &= \sqrt{2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{d}} \vec{l}_3 \times \vec{l}_1 \\ \vec{l}_3 &= -\frac{1}{2}s_{01} \times s_{02} & s_{03} &= \sqrt{2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{d}} \vec{l}_1 \times \vec{l}_2 \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

where $d = |-\vec{l}_1 \cdot (\vec{l}_2 \times \vec{l}_3)|$

Note:

$$\begin{aligned} s_{01} \cdot (s_{02} \times s_{03}) &= -2\sqrt{2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{d}} (\vec{l}_1 \cdot (\vec{l}_2 \times \vec{l}_3)) \\ V &= \frac{1}{6} |s_{01} \cdot (s_{02} \times s_{03})| = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} |-\vec{l}_1 \cdot (\vec{l}_2 \times \vec{l}_3)|^{1/2} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} d^{1/2} \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

where V is the tetrahedron volume.

Specific: $s_{01} \cdot (s_{02} \times s_{03}) > 0$ if the sequence x_1, x_2, x_3 is pictured as clockwise from x_0 . To avoid ambiguities, we use the absolute value in the formulas.

Therefore the sides and the faces representations are equivalent. We can choose an origin and 3 normals, i.e. $3 + 3 \times 3 = 3 + 9 = 12$ numbers up to translations and rotations, that is 6 numbers, hence giving again 6 degrees of freedom.

A.2 Classical geometry of two tetrahedra with a face in common

Figure 5: Composite of two tetrahedra with a face in common (outer normals shown)

A composite of two tetrahedra with a face in common is classically sketched in figure 5. It is the sum of two 3-simplices, ν_1 and ν_2 , where the 3 vertices of the face in common are identified:

$$\begin{aligned} \nu_1 + \nu_2 &= [x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3] + [x_4, x_5, x_6, x_7] = \\ &= [x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3] + [x_1, x_2, x_3, x_7] \quad \text{oriented composite} \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

It has 8 oriented faces (oriented triangles), which are 2-simplices, and that we label against the opposite vertex

$$\begin{aligned} f_0 &= [x_1, x_2, x_3] & f_1 &= -[x_0, x_2, x_3] & f_2 &= [x_0, x_1, x_3] & f_3 &= -[x_0, x_1, x_2] \\ f_4 &= [x_2, x_3, x_7] & f_5 &= -[x_1, x_3, x_7] & f_6 &= [x_1, x_2, x_7] & f_7 &= -[x_1, x_2, x_3] \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

the 2 internal faces, f_0 and f_7 , cancel each other, thus leaving 6 external faces to the composite.

As for the sides, we know from the geometry of one tetrahedron, refer to appendix A.1, that in each of them only 3 sides are independent.

Let's say

$$\begin{aligned} \nu_1 : \quad s_{01} &= [x_0, x_1] & s_{02} &= [x_0, x_2] & s_{03} &= [x_0, x_3] \\ \nu_2 : \quad s_{47} &= [x_4, x_7] & s_{57} &= [x_5, x_7] & s_{67} &= [x_6, x_7] \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

however

$$\begin{aligned} s_{47} &= [x_4, x_7] = [x_4, x_6] + [x_6, x_7] = s_{46} + s_{67} = s_{13} + s_{67} \\ s_{57} &= [x_5, x_7] = [x_5, x_6] + [x_6, x_7] = s_{56} + s_{67} = s_{23} + s_{67} \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

only 1 side in ν_2 is independent. So, the composite shows only 4 sides independent.

The composite is determined by an origin, one of the vertices, the other 3 vertices of the first tetrahedron, and the opposite vertex of the second tetrahedron, i.e. $3 + 3 \times 3 + 3 = 3 + 9 + 3 = 15$ numbers up to translations and rotations, that is $3 + 3 = 6$ numbers, hence giving $15 - 6 = 9$ degrees of freedom.

Sides representation

Or, we can choose an origin, 3 independent sides of the first tetrahedron, 1 independent side of the second tetrahedron, i.e. $3 + 3 \times 3 + 3 = 3 + 9 + 3 = 15$ numbers up to translations and rotations, that is 6 numbers, hence giving again 9 degrees of freedom.

Faces representation

As for the outer normals, let's first consider each tetrahedron at a time. In the first tetrahedron we have 3 independent outer normals: $\vec{l}_1, \vec{l}_2, \vec{l}_3$, which are equivalent to the 3 independent sides: s_{01}, s_{02}, s_{03} .

In the second tetrahedron we have 3 independent outer normals: $\vec{l}_4, \vec{l}_5, \vec{l}_6$, which are equivalent to the 3 independent sides: s_{47}, s_{57}, s_{67} , that is

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{l}_4 &= \frac{1}{2} s_{57} \times s_{67} & s_{47} &= \sqrt{2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{e}} \vec{l}_5 \times \vec{l}_6 \\ \vec{l}_5 &= \frac{1}{2} s_{67} \times s_{47} & s_{57} &= \sqrt{2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{e}} \vec{l}_6 \times \vec{l}_4 \\ \vec{l}_6 &= \frac{1}{2} s_{47} \times s_{57} & s_{67} &= \sqrt{2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{e}} \vec{l}_4 \times \vec{l}_5 \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

where $e = |\vec{l}_4 \cdot (\vec{l}_5 \times \vec{l}_6)|$

Note:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{l}_7 &= -\frac{1}{2} s_{45} \times s_{46} \\ \sum_{\beta} \vec{l}_{\beta} &= 0 \quad \beta = 4, 5, 6, 7 \quad \text{classical closure condition} \\ s_{47} \cdot (s_{57} \times s_{67}) &= 2\sqrt{2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{e}} (\vec{l}_4 \cdot (\vec{l}_5 \times \vec{l}_6)) \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

$$V = \frac{1}{6} |s_{47} \cdot (s_{57} \times s_{67})| = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} |\vec{l}_4 \cdot (\vec{l}_5 \times \vec{l}_6)|^{1/2} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} e^{1/2}$$

where V is the tetrahedron volume.

Specific: $s_{47} \cdot (s_{57} \times s_{67}) > 0$ if the sequence x_4, x_5, x_6 is pictured as anticlockwise from x_7 . To avoid ambiguities, we use the absolute value in the formulas.

However, looking at the composite, we may express the 3 outer normals of the second tetrahedron against the 3 outer normals of the first tetrahedron and a side of the second tetrahedron.

$$\begin{aligned}
\vec{l}_4 &= \frac{1}{2} s_{57} \times s_{67} = \frac{1}{2} (s_{23} + s_{67}) \times s_{67} = \frac{1}{2} (s_{03} - s_{02}) \times s_{67} = \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{d}} (\vec{l}_1 \times \vec{l}_2 - \vec{l}_3 \times \vec{l}_1) \times s_{67} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{(\vec{l}_1 \times (\vec{l}_2 + \vec{l}_3)) \times s_{67}}{\sqrt{|\vec{l}_1 \cdot (\vec{l}_2 \times \vec{l}_3)|}} \\
\vec{l}_5 &= \frac{1}{2} s_{67} \times s_{47} = \frac{1}{2} s_{67} \times (s_{13} + s_{67}) = \frac{1}{2} s_{67} \times (s_{03} - s_{01}) = \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{d}} s_{67} \times (\vec{l}_1 \times \vec{l}_2 - \vec{l}_2 \times \vec{l}_3) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{(\vec{l}_2 \times (\vec{l}_3 + \vec{l}_1)) \times s_{67}}{\sqrt{|\vec{l}_1 \cdot (\vec{l}_2 \times \vec{l}_3)|}} \\
\vec{l}_6 &= \frac{1}{2} s_{47} \times s_{57} = \frac{1}{2} (s_{13} + s_{67}) \times (s_{23} + s_{67}) = \\
&= \frac{1}{2} (s_{03} - s_{01} + s_{67}) \times (s_{03} - s_{02} + s_{67}) = \\
&= \frac{1}{2} ((s_{03} - s_{01}) \times (s_{03} - s_{02}) + (s_{03} - s_{01}) \times s_{67} + s_{67} \times (s_{03} - s_{02})) = \\
&= \frac{1}{2} (-2(\vec{l}_1 + \vec{l}_2 + \vec{l}_3) + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{d}} (\vec{l}_1 \times \vec{l}_2 - \vec{l}_2 \times \vec{l}_3) \times s_{67} + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{d}} s_{67} \times (\vec{l}_1 \times \vec{l}_2 - \vec{l}_3 \times \vec{l}_1)) = \\
&= -(\vec{l}_1 + \vec{l}_2 + \vec{l}_3) - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{(\vec{l}_2 \times (\vec{l}_3 + \vec{l}_1)) \times s_{67}}{\sqrt{|\vec{l}_1 \cdot (\vec{l}_2 \times \vec{l}_3)|}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{(\vec{l}_1 \times (\vec{l}_2 + \vec{l}_3)) \times s_{67}}{\sqrt{|\vec{l}_1 \cdot (\vec{l}_2 \times \vec{l}_3)|}} = \\
&= -(\vec{l}_1 + \vec{l}_2 + \vec{l}_3) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{(\vec{l}_3 \times (\vec{l}_1 + \vec{l}_2)) \times s_{67}}{\sqrt{|\vec{l}_1 \cdot (\vec{l}_2 \times \vec{l}_3)|}}
\end{aligned} \tag{52}$$

Note:

$$\begin{aligned}
\vec{l}_7 &= -\frac{1}{2} s_{45} \times s_{46} = -\frac{1}{2} s_{12} \times s_{13} = -\vec{l}_0 \\
f_7 &= -f_0 \quad \text{face in common} \\
\vec{l}_0 + \vec{l}_7 &= 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \vec{l}_1 + \vec{l}_2 + \vec{l}_3 + \vec{l}_4 + \vec{l}_5 + \vec{l}_6 = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{53}$$

This is the classical closure condition, applied to the composite. The same relation can be obtained summing up $\vec{l}_4, \vec{l}_5, \vec{l}_6$, expressed vs. $\vec{l}_1, \vec{l}_2, \vec{l}_3$, as per above.

So, we can write

$$\begin{aligned}
\vec{l}_4 &= \vec{l}_4(\vec{l}_1, \vec{l}_2, \vec{l}_3, s_{67}) \\
\vec{l}_5 &= \vec{l}_5(\vec{l}_1, \vec{l}_2, \vec{l}_3, s_{67}) \\
\vec{l}_6 &= \vec{l}_6(\vec{l}_1, \vec{l}_2, \vec{l}_3, s_{67})
\end{aligned} \tag{54}$$

but we can also express s_{67} vs. $\vec{l}_1, \vec{l}_2, \vec{l}_3, \vec{l}_4$, that is

$$\begin{aligned} s_{67} &= s_{67}(\vec{l}_1, \vec{l}_2, \vec{l}_3, \vec{l}_4) \\ \vec{l}_5 &= \vec{l}_5(\vec{l}_1, \vec{l}_2, \vec{l}_3, \vec{l}_4) \\ \vec{l}_6 &= \vec{l}_6(\vec{l}_1, \vec{l}_2, \vec{l}_3, \vec{l}_4) \end{aligned} \tag{55}$$

Therefore the composite shows 4 independent outer normals, in this case 3 normals from the first tetrahedron and 1 normal from the second tetrahedron, but we could choose also 2 normals from the first and 2 normals from the second, or 1 normal from the first and 3 normals from the second.

The 4 independent outer normals of the composite, $\vec{l}_1, \vec{l}_2, \vec{l}_3, \vec{l}_4$, can be expressed against the 4 independent sides, $s_{01}, s_{02}, s_{03}, s_{67}$, and vice versa. Hence the sides and faces representations of the composite are equivalent.

So, as for the composite, we can choose an origin and 4 normals, i.e. $3 + 4 \times 3 = 3 + 12 = 15$ numbers up to translations and rotations, that is 6 numbers, hence giving again 9 degrees of freedom.

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